

**Project SOP D-JRP17-
WP2.SOP1 – Questionnaire
for Brucellosis research
Workpackage 2**

Responsible Partner: INIAV

Contributing partners: ANSES, BfR, INSA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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QUESTIONNAIRE FOR BRUCELLOSIS RESEARCH

Questionnaire for Brucellosis research

Service/Laboratory: _____
 Hospital: _____

Sample number: _____
 Date and Hour: _____

Patient Information

N° clinic process: _____
 Name of doctor: _____
 Service: _____ Room: _____ Bed: _____
 Date of hospital stay: ___/___/___ (dd/mm/aa)

Patient Information (Name): _____
 Sex Date of birth Age
 Women Man ___/___/___ (aa/mm/dd) _____
 _____(months/years)

Address _____

Clinical Informaion
 Symptomatology: _____

Therapy Information

Antibiotherapy prior to harvesting the biological product? yes No unknown
 Ik yes, which one? _____

Biological sample information

Biological sample
 Cerebrospinal fluid Tissue Blood culture Serum Strain

Other (specify)) _____

Strain
 Reference of strain _____ Isolation date _____

Epidemiological information

- Isolated case Outbreak
 Infected animals contact food intake, specify _____
 Professional exposure

Geographical origin

- Country City: _____
 Other country Specify: _____